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NLR regulation of the TSC family.

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Both NOD2 and NLRC4 could influence or control expression of TSC22D nutrient sensor genes including control of TSC22D4 by NOD2.

Citations

1. Demir, S., Wolff, G., Wieder, A., Maida, A., Bühler, L., Brune, M., Hautzinger, O., Feuchtinger, A., Poth, T., Szendroedi, J. and Herzig, S., 2022. TSC22D4 interacts with Akt1 to regulate glucose metabolism. *Science Advances*, 8(42), p.eabo5555.